

Pomadasys commersonnii Spotted Grunter

Decoding
South Africa's
Biodiversity

© Craig Peter

Group: Bony Fish

Size: 80 cm Total Length

Distribution:

This species is found in the Southeast Atlantic and Western Indian Ocean. Its range includes South Africa's Western and Eastern Cape coasts, extending along East Africa, the Persian Gulf, Socotra, the Seychelles, and Madagascar, reaching as far as the northwest coast of India.

Importance:

The Spotted Grunter is a high-value species targeted by commercial fisheries. In South Africa, commercial fishing of this species is prohibited, with only recreational angling permitted. Due to its desirable traits, the Spotted Grunter also shows strong potential for development within the aquaculture industry.

PromethION Sequencing Report:

Output: 37.78 Gigabases

Approximate N50: 5.82 kilobases

Draft Genome Assembly Statistics:

Genome Length: 0.69 Gigabases

BUSCO completeness score: 98.4% [Single: 95.3%, Duplicated: 3.1%]

Assembly N50: 802.31 kilobases

Contig number: 3 309

Sample Contributor contact details:

Dr Gwynneth Matcher

South African Institute for Aquatic Biodiversity

g.matcher@saiab.nrf.ac.za

DIPLOMICS
CONNECTING RESEARCHERS & WORLD CLASS OMICS FACILITIES

Date Published: 2025-07-23
DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.16356056